

ABOUT THE ISSUE OF STRATEGIC THINKING IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Mastering a foreign language is divided into two stages - passive and active. With passive knowledge, the main role is played by recognition (the involuntary aspect of memory work), and with active knowledge, recall (search for information in memory, i.e. a more difficult process). A special issue in teaching is strategic thinking and the use of interactive technologies in the classroom. In the process of teaching students a foreign language, along with practical classes, lectures of a linguistic, regional studies and methodological nature play an important role. Practical language classes are also important, which require students' indispensable foreign language speech activity. The listed issues are discussed in this article, which is based on a large amount of methodological material.*

Keywords: *foreign language, strategy, communicative strategy, memorization, method, technique, thinking, pedagogical technologies, technical teaching aids, lecture and practical lesson.*

1. Introduction

Learning a foreign language presents difficulties at different stages of acquisition. The purpose of the research in this article is to consider some of the methods and techniques that have been most widely used recently in the teaching of foreign languages, including the Korean language. To achieve this goal, we set the task of considering the methods and techniques of teaching a foreign language using the example of Korean, and analyzing the introduction of pedagogical technologies in teaching the Korean language.

Recently, much attention has been paid to learning a foreign language as a second foreign language. This problem of language learning requires in-depth research. In addition, an important issue is strategic thinking in learning, for example, memorizing a huge number of foreign words, grammatical structures, and structural features. The learning process, however, can be facilitated by using individual observation and the ability to organize the material being studied. As in any field of knowledge, here you should connect newly acquired information with existing information. This involves building bridges between the native culture and the culture of the people speaking the language being studied. The acquisition of a foreign language is facilitated by such techniques as visualization, association of images and writing short stories.

Systematic, purposeful acquisition of knowledge and skills presupposes a certain level of memory development, including voluntary, logical, i.e. memory based on understanding, on special mental processing of material for the purpose of memorizing and reproducing it [5]. The organization of knowledge assimilation processes also plays a certain role in the strength of memorization; in particular, several approaches to the organization of such processes have been developed in psychology. The typical structure of the assimilation process includes perception, understanding, comprehension, generalization, consolidation, and application. It is important to emphasize that all of the above elements of assimilation exist, not in isolation. Already during

perception there are some initial elements of understanding and comprehension. Most often, the problem of learning foreign languages is largely related to the problem of memory [6]. The essence of the process of language acquisition lies in a series of sequential acts of memorization. However, we note that the problem is not so much in memorization as in retaining the material in memory.

In the process of teaching a foreign language to students, along with practical classes, lectures of a linguistic, regional and methodological nature play an important role, which, if not read entirely in the target language, then at least involve it to one degree or another. If practical language classes presuppose the indispensable foreign language speech activity of students, then the traditional role of listeners in lecture classes is passive, which allows the teacher to present a larger amount of information, saving time on its discussion [1,2]. This situation apparently contributes to more successful implementation of teacher-led knowledge acquisition. However, currently there is a transition to a competent approach, which is focused not so much on the accumulation of knowledge, but on the ability to creatively use it in one's activities. Accordingly, the teacher is required not only to ensure the transfer of knowledge, but also to create conditions for the development of skills to freely operate with the information received. In this regard, there is a need to introduce new ideas and teaching methods into the educational process.

2. Strategic thinking in learning

Recently, many experts have proposed stimulating students' cognitive activity through the introduction of interactive technologies into the learning process. Interactive learning, which is essentially one of the varieties of communication technologies, presupposes well-organized feedback between the teacher and the student with a two-way exchange of information between them (which is all the more important if there is a need to train students in the use of the language in which the teaching is conducted). When working in an interactive mode, information received from the teacher into the student's mind causes active mental activity of the latter, generating a reverse information flow. Of course, even during a traditional lecture, the information coming from the teacher to one degree or another stimulates the mental activity of the students [8]. However, the thoughts that arise in the listeners of such a lecture do not necessarily imply their expression. This allows some students to avoid immediate comprehension of the issues presented in class, limiting themselves to more or less detailed recording of ready-made information received from the teacher (which does little to promote intellectual development).

With interactive learning, the very structure of the lesson should ensure the inclusion of students' thinking, even before they receive the full amount of necessary information - as this is realized, for example, in a lecture of a problematic nature. The theoretical material at such a lecture is given in the form of a problematic task, in the process of solving which a dialogue arises (both external and internal) [9]. No less important in learning is the principle of clarity. In addition to the fact that the image provides visual support, serving as an illustration of the information being communicated, it can also serve as a support for adequate mental and practical actions. In particular, the so-called lecture-visualization is based on this. In preparation for it, educational information is recoded into visual form through diagrams, drawings, drawings, etc., and during the lecture itself, a coherent, detailed commentary on visual materials is carried out. Modern technical teaching aids can provide invaluable assistance to the teacher in organizing such classes. In particular, the necessary images can be shown on the screen using a projector or using an interactive whiteboard. In addition, the most important terms and definitions can be presented this way [4]. The latter is especially relevant, for example, in the case of language classes in which students do not speak a foreign language well enough. In this case, graphic presentation of new

terms allows listeners to avoid mistakes in their recording. Presenting them by demonstrating relevant slides, rather than writing on the board, allows the teacher to both save time and more successfully maintain eye contact with the audience.

However, one should not abuse modern technical means, considering their use as an indispensable, and even more so, sufficient, condition for conducting classes using modern teaching technologies. Thus, it is hardly worth displaying the same information (and not just key points and illustrations) on the screen at the same time as the oral presentation of information. This causes rapid addiction and shifts the main attention of listeners from the lecturer to the screen - and as a result, a situation arises in which modern technologies in teaching (multimedia, etc.), if used incorrectly, hinder the implementation of no less modern interactive educational technologies. Moreover, modern teaching technologies can be successfully implemented in the classroom without the use of any technical means [2]. An example would be a lecture for two, which involves discussing problematic issues from different positions by two specialists (for example, a theorist and a practitioner). During the discussion, listeners are drawn into communication (including foreign language), ask questions, form and express their own attitude to the problem under discussion, demonstrating a mental and behavioral response to what is happening.

In addition, with the help of interactive technology, you can develop the ability to critically analyze incoming information and identify false information, which is important for the formation of independent thinking. A lesson with pre-planned errors is aimed at solving this problem. The content of such a lesson initially includes errors of a substantive, methodological and behavioral nature, a list of which is presented to students at the end. Usually 10-15 minutes are allocated to analyze errors noted by students during the lesson. Naturally, it is better to give such a lecture when students already have sufficient knowledge of the problem under consideration.

An equally interesting form of conducting a lesson using interactive technologies is a lecture in the form of a press conference. The teacher names the topic of the lecture, after which he asks the listeners to ask him questions about it in writing, for which no more than 5 minutes are allocated [7]. For about the same amount of time (or a little longer), the lecturer sorts the questions received, and then, based on their semantic content, presents the lecture in the form of a coherent presentation of the topic. At the end of the lecture, the questions asked are certainly assessed, reflecting the knowledge and interests of the students. There are a number of other forms of delivering lectures using interactive technologies. However, it must be borne in mind that classes of this type place increased demands on both students and the teacher himself, who must be fluent in the material and teaching language, as well as be open to communication with the audience.

3. Training in speech activity

Before moving on to a description of methodological work on oral speech at different stages of learning, let us briefly dwell on some linguistic and psychological features of oral speech, keeping in mind in this case that oral foreign language speech is the goal of learning. Understanding these features is necessary, first of all, in order to clearly distinguish between oral speech as a goal and oral speech as a means of learning. In the first case, students' speech products must have the basic features inherent in oral speech as such, in the second case we are talking about so-called oral exercises, during which other tasks are solved, and therefore the oral pronunciation of lexical, grammatical, phonetic units or their combinations also not in all cases are

characterized by parameters inherent in speech communication, since students often operate with isolated linguistic units, which in itself deprives them of communicative content.

Speaking about the main linguistic features of oral speech, it is necessary first of all to emphasize its difference from written speech, which is of no small importance considering that in most cases oral foreign language speech is still taught using written speech material [9].

Oral utterance differs from written speech primarily in the direct nature of communication, the presence of live contact between communicants, which, of course, leaves a strong imprint on the method and form of presentation of thoughts. The presence of a speech interlocutor or simply listeners makes it possible for the speaker to catch the slightest reaction of his interlocutors in a speech act, and this makes it possible to “adjust” all the time, to quickly respond to the further course of the presentation of thoughts in oral form.

Of course, educational oral speech with these characteristics may differ significantly from that which can be heard from the lips of native speakers entering into dialogue in some narrow area of communication. However, its advantage in methodological terms is that it, being understandable to everyone who speaks a given language, and, in addition, it is, as a rule, simpler in forms of expression, more standardized, which makes it easier to master its basics and use it for the purpose of communications.

When describing the teaching methodology, we will keep in mind the following four prerequisites for successful mastery of oral foreign language speech: a) monologue and dialogic forms of oral speech are studied at all stages in parallel; b) an integrated approach to language acquisition is carried out, which means simultaneous teaching of oral speech and reading, sequential implementation of preparatory (language) and speech exercises; c) increased density of use of learning aids; d) widespread use of oral speech tasks. As you know, in most educational institutions, work on the language in continuing groups begins with the so-called “remedial course”[3,4]. The main goal is to establish the level of language training of students and, on this basis, to level out knowledge, skills and abilities, as far as possible, which will make it possible to set more or less homogeneous tasks for students of all groups in the future. After completing the “corrective course”, which, by the way, is built to a large extent on prepared dialogical oral speech and even more on oral exercises, you can begin systematic mastery of those objects of oral speech that constitute the essence of the educational process at this stage.

In order to be able to speak and understand speech, a person must attract various types of memory, which were mentioned above. It should be considered fair that when teaching foreign languages, involuntary memorization is of particular importance. This is due to the fact that simply memorizing words, their grammatical forms, etc. cannot ensure participation in communication. It is necessary to develop the ability to use language material, and not just memorize. You can voluntarily remember only individual speech clichés, clichés, phrases, words, poems; voluntary memorization should occupy an insignificant place in the overall learning process. “An extremely important feature of the process of involuntary memorization is the reduction of the barrier of memory selectivity, the removal of “anxiety” in students associated with memory uncertainty. The great effectiveness of involuntary memorization has now been proven with complete convincing. Therefore, the analysis of those conditions that ensure the most favorable course of the process of involuntary memorization is of particular importance.” The point of view that focuses our attention on the combination of voluntary and involuntary memory in the practice of teaching a foreign language also deserves attention.

The above allows us to formulate our theoretical position. It is as follows: the essence of the memory problem in mastering a foreign language is in the optimal combination of memory in voluntary and involuntary and in the maximum involvement of mental processes in the work of memory, since teaching the art of thinking also means teaching the art of using memory: through mental operations we are able to find in it the basic elements on which one can rely when mastering the new thing that is being studied at the moment. At the same time, it is important to most accurately determine in each case the object and purpose of memorization and clearly organize the student's educational activity psychologically, without relying on the fact that a certain number of repetitions in itself ensures that the necessary units are "imprinted" in memory.

Each stage (perception, memorization, forgetting, storage, recollection) is important for the functioning of memory as a whole. And on each it is possible to use special methods for optimizing memory performance. The same information can be remembered in different ways. Memory is an important mechanism for the socialization of the individual, and at all stages of education. We live in the information age, where meaning plays a leading role. Everything bad is rejected, but not enough good is created. Creativity and independence are not always encouraged at school. Homework often does not help develop memory. There is no single concept that reveals the integrity of the educational process at the university. But it is precisely this social institution that should prepare future specialists, professionals with a solid knowledge base. The socialization of the individual cannot proceed successfully without such a factor as the development of memory, and, at the same time, memory cannot exist outside of society. Hence, the interaction and interdependence of two processes is obvious: socialization and memory. This method is closely related to the basic principle that a word can always be placed in its proper context, and is very effective. You mentally build bridges between the general idea and this or that detail and, if possible, you yourself look for the most successful schemes for presenting new material. It has been proven that the most effective teaching strategy is for the student to actively search for his or her own patterns, principles, or other relationships and connections in the area being studied. That is why it is recommended to combine the study of already established rules with the search for some connections that you have personally noticed.

Mastering a foreign language can be divided into two stages - passive and active. With passive knowledge, the main role is played by recognition (the involuntary aspect of memory work), and with active knowledge, recall (search for information in memory, i.e. a more difficult process). In the first stage, being familiar with sounds, words and syntactic structures, you understand what is being said and what is written. In the next stage, you take an active role and speak, write and think freely in the foreign language [5].

However, ease in conversation is achieved only at the cost of continuous practice. When you no longer need to use a foreign language, you get the impression that you are losing this skill. The speed and extent of its loss depends on the method in which you acquired it. If you have a solid foundation in understanding a foreign language and its structures, it comes back to you very quickly once you are back in an environment where that language is spoken. However, without theoretical and formal knowledge, language recall can be much more difficult. Emotions also play a big role here: friendships with foreigners increase motivation, creating an additional incentive.

When determining an aid, it is necessary first of all to take into account the very wide range of available means, both non-technical and technical [9]. In accordance with this, only traditional visual aids - tables, pictures, diagrams, etc., which, in fact, are not special for teaching foreign languages and are therefore widely used in the study of many other academic subjects cannot be

classified as auxiliary teaching aids. On the contrary, special means should include, first of all, those that show their specificity specifically in teaching languages. Here we mean means of auditory visualization, i.e. background materials of various types. Other technical devices, including such complex ones as electronic classrooms, electronic computers, etc., can also be classified as auxiliary means, if they are used in teaching a foreign language.

Thus, by auxiliary teaching aids, if we define them in the most general form, we should understand a wide variety of materials and tools of the educational process, thanks to the use of which the set learning goals are achieved more successfully and in a rationally reduced time. The main purpose of auxiliary means is to bring the implementation of the educational process closer to optimal characteristics, and in teaching foreign languages, in most cases, to create a more or less pronounced illusion of familiarization with a foreign language environment, with the conditions in which close to natural functioning of the foreign language being studied takes place.

4. Functional teaching of foreign language vocabulary

The essence of functional teaching of foreign language vocabulary lies in such an organization of the learning process that takes into account the entire complex of factors that influence the strong acquisition of lexical units and their communicative and successful use in foreign language communication. These factors include: students' activities in mastering foreign words, ways of organizing lexical material, a system of lexical exercises.

The need to prepare students to perceive and memorize new foreign language vocabulary is due to the fact that the student acts as a subject of mastering foreign language vocabulary, and the final result of learning a foreign language depends on what specific activity and how he performs it [4].

Psychologists note that for productive memorization of any material, it is necessary, first of all, to have a need (need, need) for its perception and assimilation. The motive for schoolchildren's activities in mastering foreign language vocabulary should be the need to express their thoughts in a foreign language. It is the need to express their thoughts, emotions and mood that forms in students the need for foreign words necessary for their most accurate expression or for understanding the thoughts of the interlocutor. In this situation, conditions are created under which the student's attention is directed to the content of the statement, its meaning, as a result of which the thought itself, expressed by adequate foreign language lexical and grammatical means, is remembered. In communicative-oriented vocabulary teaching, the emphasis is not on memorizing a list of foreign words, but on remembering the thought, the meaning of the statement, which fully corresponds to the reproduction and use of words in real communication: when communicating in our native language, we remember not words, but thoughts expressed with their help.

Thus, the "importance of preparing students to meet new words" becomes obvious, the essence of which is to make the presented foreign words meaningful for students both semantically and emotionally. This, in turn, means that the subjects of mental activity should be relevant and interesting for students [7].

To evoke students' thoughts and, accordingly, evoke the need to use foreign words, it is necessary to present an extralinguistic object that would prompt students to want to share their thoughts, emotions, and feelings. In modern domestic and foreign educational and methodological complexes, story-based pictures, photographs, and short videos accompanied by problem-based tasks are used for this purpose. Problematic speech-thinking tasks can be based on conjecture,

assumption, classification, interpretation, finding similarities and differences, judgment, etc. In this way evoking a special functional state of students, we set the following tasks:

- a) targeted activation of previously studied lexical material;
- b) purposeful assimilation by schoolchildren of a pre-selected and organized list of words.

Functional teaching of vocabulary requires its specific organization, which is due, on the one hand, to the modern goals of teaching a foreign language - the formation of the ability and readiness for foreign language communication, and on the other hand, to the specifics of the functioning of the human brain, because It is the brain that receives and processes all the information received by the body from the external environment. The main goal of lexical exercises is to create a strong image of a word in the students' memory, for which it is necessary to create an extensive and widest connection of this particular foreign language word with other foreign words and with equivalents of the corresponding word in their native language. It has been proven that a word in a foreign language does not automatically "inherit" the entire complex of connections that determines the activity of its equivalent in the native language. For: to ensure the activity of a foreign language word in speech and mental activity, it is necessary to form a special network of connections with other words. At first, the inclusion of a foreign word in speech is regulated by the categorical behavior of the equivalent word in the native language. Thus, the goal of lexical exercises is to create a cognitive (mental) image of a word in students' memory through the formation of stable associative connections of each word with the topic and situation of communication, as well as with other lexical units.

Conclusion

Thus, we examined strategic thinking in learning a foreign language. In the process of analyzing methods and techniques in teaching, we made the following conclusions:

- each stage (perception, memorization, forgetting, preservation, recollection) is important for the functioning of memory as a whole;
- the socialization of the individual cannot take place successfully without such a factor as the development of memory, and, at the same time, memory cannot exist outside of society. Hence, the interaction and interdependence of two processes is obvious: socialization and memory;
- mastering a foreign language can be divided into two stages – passive and active. With passive knowledge, the main role is played by recognition (the involuntary aspect of memory work), and with active knowledge, recall (the search for information in memory, i.e. the process is more difficult);
- depending on the way we process the information we want to remember, we will retain it in memory better or worse.

Education should ensure not only the full personal, social, and cultural development of students, but also readiness for further development or self-education. The goal of teaching foreign languages at the present stage, in particular the Korean language, is the formation of communicative competence, which includes linguistic, thematic (extralinguistic and regional information), socio-cultural, compensatory, educational (the ability to learn). The student must master such skills and abilities that would allow for the most successful specialized training and would provide the opportunity to self-study foreign languages in several directions: maintaining and improving the achieved level of communicative competence and learning a new foreign language.

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